

SOCIO-ECONOMIC RELATIONS IN MOVAROUNNAHR IN THE 20S-80S OF THE 13TH CENTURY AFTER THE MONGOL INVASION

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Abstract In this article, I have discussed the Mongol rule and their foreign policy in the territory of Movarounnahr between the 20s and 80s of the 13th century. After the Mongol invasion, many cities were turned into ruins. Half of the population was exterminated by the Mongols, while another part died of starvation. The territories of Movarounnahr were left in ruins. Later, reconstruction work began during the period of the Mongol khans and was completed during the Timurid era.

Keywords Movarounnahr, Mongols, Samarkand, Bukhara, Merv, Balkh, Khwarezm, Khorasan, Genghis Khan, Chagatai, Mongke, Alghu, Golden Horde, Mubarak Shah, Baraq Khan, Kaidu Khan, Ogedei, Iran, Afghanistan, Amu Darya, Syr Darya.

INTRODUCTION In the 13th century, a new dynasty was established in Movarounnahr under Mongol rule, which took the name of the Chagatai Ulus. After the Mongol invasion, the Chagatai Ulus carried out restoration work in this region. Various efforts were made by the rulers to rebuild the destroyed cities and improve the living conditions of the population. During the period of the Chagatai Ulus, Movarounnahr began to rebuild its life once again.

MAIN PART After the Mongol invasion, the once-prosperous regions of Movarounnahr, Khwarezm, and Khorasan were completely devastated. Ancient, well-known prosperous cities in the East, including Samarkand, Bukhara, Urgench, Khujand, Merv, Termez, Balkh, and Nishapur, were turned into ruins. Following the invasion, the production of fine silk fabrics, jewelry, weaponry, and the weaving of decorative silk fabrics, for which the East was famous, also came to an end.

During his lifetime, Genghis Khan distributed territories to his sons as "ulus" (domains). As early as 1207, he gave his eldest son lands ranging from the Selenga River to the Irtysh. In 1225, while still alive, Genghis Khan completely divided the conquered territories among his sons. The territories from Southern Siberia to Khwarezm and Derbent were given to Jochi; the lands from the southern borders of the Altai Mountains to the Amu Darya and Syr Darya were given to his second son, Chagatai; China and Mongolia were inherited by his third son, Ogedei; and Iran and Khorasan were given to Tolui as an ulus.

According to Rashid al-Din, after Genghis Khan's death, Chagatai received 4,000 soldiers. Their leaders belonged to the Barlas, Jalayir, Qavchin, and Arlat tribes. According to Arabshah, the Qavchins lived north of the Amu Darya and in the eastern parts of Bukhara. The Barlas were located in the Kashkadarya oasis, and the Arlats were in northern Afghanistan. Because these territories were ruled by Genghis Khan's second son, Chagatai, they became known as the Chagatai Ulus. As a result of internal wars among the Mongols, Mongke (1251–1259) came to the throne in 1251 with the support of Batu Khan and Berke Khan. His first action was to abolish the Chagatai Ulus as a domain and divide it with Batu Khan. Later, after Mongke's death, Chagatai's grandson Alghu Khan (1261–1266) fought against the Golden Horde and restored the Chagatai Ulus as a state.

In the 60s and 70s of the 13th century, the empire, which was officially considered a single entity, actually split into several independent parts. For example, it broke into nearly independent sections such as the Hulaguids (Ilkhanate) in Iran, the Chagatais in Movarounnahr, and the Golden Horde. Each ulus appointed its own independent khans and occasionally waged wars against one another. Thus, the vast empire disintegrated into independent domains.

Alghu died between 1263 and 1264. Consequently, Kublai Khan, in order to establish political control over the wealthy territories of Movarounnahr, sent people sympathetic to him—namely Mubarak Shah and Baraq Khan—to the Chagatai Ulus.

Mubarak Shah was appointed khan of the Chagatai Ulus in the spring of 1264 in the Akhangaran Valley. According to the decree sent by Kublai Khan, Baraq Khan could take the throne after Mubarak Shah. Mubarak Shah gave Baraq Khan the title of "Barshchi." Mubarak Shah was the first Chagatai khan to convert to Islam. He is considered to have converted to the new religion in the Akhangaran Valley of the Tashkent oasis, where he ascended the throne. Because of this conversion, the Mongols began to unite around Baraq Khan against Mubarak Shah. In the autumn of 1265, the forces of Mubarak Shah and his opponent Baraq Khan clashed in Khujand; as a result of the battle, Baraq Khan emerged victorious.

Baraq Khan ascended the throne of the Chagatai Ulus at the beginning of 1266. He soon completely subjugated Movarounnahr and fully freed it from Mongol (central) influence. For instance, around 1266, the troops sent by Kublai Khan to subjugate Baraq Khan to Mongolia were expelled from Eastern Turkestan. Consequently, Baraq Khan succeeded in taking actual control of the Chagatai Ulus. Prior to this, the khans of the Chagatai Ulus were to some extent dependent on the Great Khan. In 1268, a war broke out between Baraq Khan and Kaidu Khan, who was ruling the northeastern part of the Chagatai Ulus. Due to the intervention of the Golden Horde khan, Mongke-Temur, the war ended with a peace treaty. In 1269, a Kurultai (assembly) was convened in the Talas Valley, where Mongke-Temur, Kaidu, and Baraq Khan participated and agreed on their mutual borders. According to this agreement, two-thirds of Movarounnahr was given to Baraq Khan, and one-third was given to Kaidu Khan. Additionally, Kaidu Khan was to provide military assistance to Baraq Khan in his campaigns against Khorasan. In the spring of 1270, Baraq Khan marched on Khorasan with a large army. In the initial battle, the army led by Abaqa's brother, Tubshin, and Amir Arghun was defeated by Baraq Khan. Soon after, the amirs sent by Kaidu Khan deserted. As a result, in the decisive battle with Abaqa, Baraq Khan was defeated. Returning to Movarounnahr, Baraq Khan became paralyzed and died in 1271. Now, the Chagatai Ulus fell under the influence of Kaidu Khan. This process lasted for 30 years. Kaidu Khan controlled the territory of Movarounnahr until his death. Kaidu Khan appointed the khans himself, and in 1285, he appointed Duwa Khan (1285–1307). After Kaidu Khan's death, starting from 1303, the Chagatai Ulus regained its full independence in Movarounnahr.

Conclusion In conclusion, the period from the 20s to the 80s of the 13th century was a time of great hardship for the common people. During this period, the Mongols destroyed everything in their path, including cities and water reservoirs. As a result, the common population faced difficulties and stopped engaging in agriculture, which was their main source of labor. Due to hunger and various forms of oppression, people were forced to abandon the cities where they were born and raised, such as Samarkand and Bukhara. The situation during this period was very grave, which is why rulers eventually attempted to alleviate the circumstances.

References

1. Akbar Zamonov, Sardorbek Abdusodiqov, *History of Uzbekistan*, Tashkent 2024.
2. A.A. Sagdullayev, *History of Uzbekistan*, Tashkent 2020.
3. R.H. Murtazayev, *History of Uzbekistan*, Tashkent 2005.
4. Q. Usmonov, M. Sodiqov, S. Burxonova, *History of Uzbekistan*, 2006.